

ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ АСИНХРОННОЇ МАШИНИ ЯК СПОЖИВАЧА РЕАКТИВНОЇ ПОТУЖНОСТІ

Клюєв О.В.

доцент кафедри електротехніки та електромеханіки
Дніпровський державний технічний університет
м. Кам'янське, Україна
ORCID 0000-0003-4542-3317

Хмельницький Є.Д.

доцент кафедри електротехніки та електромеханіки
Дніпровський державний технічний університет
м. Кам'янське, Україна
ORCID 0000-0002-8605-4960

Рафієв Г.І.

здобувач третього (доктор філософії) рівня
Дніпровський державний технічний університет
м. Кам'янське, Україна

INVESTIGATION OF AN ASYNCHRONOUS MACHINE AS A CONSUMER OF REACTIVE POWER

Kliuiev O.,

Ph.D. technical of science, associate professor
Dniprovsk State Technical University
Kamianske, Ukraine
ORCID 0000-0003-4542-3317

Khmelnytskyi E.,

Ph.D. technical of science, associate professor
Dniprovsk State Technical University
Kamianske, Ukraine
ORCID 0000-0002-8605-4960

Rafiyev H.

the third (Doctor of Philosophy) level
Dniprovsk State Technical University
Kamianske, Ukraine

АНОТАЦІЯ

У статті виходячи з системи рівнянь асинхронної машини отримана залежність її реактивної потужності від величини напруги мережі живлення. Зроблено фізичне обґрунтування унімодальності цієї функції і наявності точки мінімуму.

ABSTRACT

In the article based on the system of equations of an asynchronous machine the dependence of its reactive power on the voltage of the power supply network is obtained. A physical justification of the unimodality of this function and the existence of a minimum point has been made.

Ключові слова: асинхронна машина, реактивна потужність, статична стійкість, екстремальні значення напруги.

Keywords: asynchronous machine, reactive power, static stability, extreme voltage values.

Introduction. A typical generalized static characteristic of a power supply node in terms of reactive power, obtained for the typical load composition in electrical networks, represents a unimodal function, i.e., the characteristic of reactive power $Q(U)$ has a V-shaped character with a minimum point. It is the presence of a minimum in the static characteristics of load nodes $Q(U)$ that determines the possibility of the development of such instability as a voltage avalanche. Such a mode is especially dangerous for industrial units with sharply changing loads (rolling mills, arc furnaces), which can create significant fluctuations in the supply voltage which significantly affects the operation of powerful asynchronous motors [1,2]. At the same time it should be taken into account that approximately

75% of the consumed reactive power is accounted for by asynchronous machines (AM) and power transformers [2]. In addition it can be added that the same physical processes occur in asynchronous machines and transformers and are described by the same equations in which only the speed of rotation of the secondary circuits is assumed to be zero for transformers. It should be said that the literature sources do not explain why the V-shaped characteristic $Q(U)$ of load nodes is so important. Therefore it is worth assuming that the dependence properties for the load node are determined by the properties of the predominant type of load namely asynchronous machines and transformers. Therefore it is expedient to obtain and investigate the characteristic $Q(U)$ for an asynchronous machine as

the main consumer of electricity which largely determines the properties of the generalized curve $Q(U)$ of the entire load node.

The task is to obtain the dependence of the reactive power of an asynchronous machine with a short-circuited rotor on the voltage of the supply network, as well as to determine the criteria for controlling the flows of reactive power in order to reduce the voltage at the load node inadmissibly.

Presentation of the main material. In the study we will depart from the usual AM substitution schemes and rely on the original statics equations. Formula for calculating reactive power

$$Q_s = \frac{3}{2}(U_{sv}I_{su} - U_{su}I_{sv}). \quad (1)$$

In the coordinate axes oriented along the stator voltage vector, formula (1) is simplified due to the fact that $U_{sv} = 0$, $U_{su} = U_s$ and then

$$Q_s = -\frac{3}{2}U_s I_{sv}. \quad (2)$$

The active power of the stator under the specified conditions is equal to

$$P_s = \frac{3}{2}(U_{su}I_{su} + U_{sv}I_{sv}) = \frac{3}{2}U_s I_{su}. \quad (3)$$

The equations of AM dynamics in the generalized axes u, v are well known and are given in many literary sources, for example [3]. We specify these equations in statics directing their coordinate axes along the stator voltage vector \vec{U}_s to obtain the projection of the stator current I_{sv} :

equation of electrical voltage balance:

$$U_s = R_s I_{su} - \omega_0 \Psi_{sv}; \quad 0 = R_s I_{sv} + \omega_0 \Psi_{su}; \quad (4)$$

$$0 = R_r I_{ru} - \omega_0 s \Psi_{rv}; \quad 0 = R_r I_{rv} + \omega_0 s \Psi_{ru}; \quad (5)$$

equations of flux linkages:

$$\Psi_{su} = L_s I_{su} + L_m I_{ru}; \quad \Psi_{sv} = L_s I_{sv} + L_m I_{rv}; \quad (6)$$

$$\Psi_{ru} = L_r I_{ru} + L_m I_{su}; \quad \Psi_{rv} = L_r I_{rv} + L_m I_{sv}; \quad (7)$$

electromagnetic moment equation

$$M_e = M_c = \frac{3}{2}NL_m(I_{sv}I_{ru} - I_{su}I_{rv}), \quad (8)$$

which in the steady state is equal to the moment of the static load.

If we set the active resistance of the stator windings equal to zero ($R_s = 0$), then from equations (4) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{su} = 0; \quad U_s = -\omega_0 \Psi_{sv} \Rightarrow \\ \Psi_{sv} = -U_s / \omega_0. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

From the first equation (6) we obtain

$$0 = L_s I_{su} + L_m I_{ru} \Rightarrow I_{su} = -k_s I_{ru}, \quad (10)$$

where $k_s = L_m / L_s$, $k_r = L_m / L_r$.

The expression for the current projection I_{ru} is determined from the equation for the electromagnetic

moment (8) taking into account expressions (9) and (10):

$$I_{ru} = -\frac{2M_c \omega_0}{3Nk_s U_s}. \quad (11)$$

We substitute the relation for flux linkages (7) into the rotor voltage equation (5) and after transformations we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} R_r I_{ru} = X_r s I_{rv} + X_m s I_{sv}; \\ -R_r I_{rv} = X_r s I_{ru} + X_m s I_{su}, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $X_m = \omega_0 L_m$; $X_r = \omega_0 L_r$; $X_s = \omega_0 L_s$.

Then taking into account (10) and expression (11) from the second equation (12) we determine the formula for the current projection I_{rv} :

$$I_{rv} = \frac{2M_c \omega_0 s}{3Nk_s R_r U_s} (X_r - k_s X_m). \quad (13)$$

Substitute the second equation (6) into the first equation (4):

$$\begin{aligned} U_s = -X_s I_{sv} - X_m I_{rv} \Rightarrow \\ I_{sv} = -\frac{U_s}{X_s} - k_s I_{rv}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Substitute formula (13) into (14):

$$I_{sv} = -\frac{U_s}{X_s} - \frac{2M_c \omega_0 s}{3NR_r U_s} (X_r - k_s X_m). \quad (15)$$

Next from formula (2) taking into account the expressions for projections I_{ru} and I_{sv} we obtain the formula for reactive power

$$Q_s = \frac{3U_s^2}{2X_s} + \frac{M_c \omega_0 s}{NR_r} (X_r - k_s X_m). \quad (16)$$

The current projection I_{su} is obtained from expression (10) taking into account (11):

$$I_{su} = \frac{2M_c \omega_0}{3NU_s}. \quad (17)$$

Substitute (17) into (3) and obtain the expression for active power

$$P_s = \frac{M_c \omega_0}{N}, \quad (18)$$

which taking into account (8) can be transformed into the following form

$$P_s = \frac{3}{2}X_m (I_{sv}I_{ru} - I_{su}I_{rv}). \quad (19)$$

Let's express the currents in formula (19) in terms of machine parameters, stator voltage and slip. First we substitute the equations of flux linkages (6), (7) into the equations of electric voltages (4), (5) and, taking into account the accepted assumption $R_s = 0$, write the system of equations obtained in this way in matrix form:

$$\begin{pmatrix} -X_s & 0 & -X_m & 0 \\ 0 & X_s & 0 & X_m \\ -X_m s & 0 & -X_r s & R_r \\ 0 & X_m s & R_r & X_r s \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I_{sv} \\ I_{su} \\ I_{rv} \\ I_{ru} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} U_s \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

From the system (20) we find the currents according to the ratios:

$$I_{sv} = \frac{\Delta_{sv}}{\Delta}; I_{su} = \frac{\Delta_{su}}{\Delta}; I_{rv} = \frac{\Delta_{rv}}{\Delta}; I_{ru} = \frac{\Delta_{ru}}{\Delta}, \quad (21)$$

where the determinants included in (21) are equal to:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= \begin{vmatrix} -X_s & 0 & -X_m & 0 \\ 0 & X_s & 0 & X_m \\ -X_m s & 0 & -X_r s & R_r \\ 0 & X_m s & R_r & X_r s \end{vmatrix} = (X_s X_r - X_m^2) s^2 + X_s^2 R_r^2; \\ \Delta_{sv} &= \begin{vmatrix} U_s & 0 & -X_m & 0 \\ 0 & X_s & 0 & X_m \\ 0 & 0 & -X_r s & R_r \\ 0 & X_m s & R_r & X_r s \end{vmatrix} = -U_s X_r (X_s X_r - X_m^2) s^2 - U_s X_s R_r^2; \\ \Delta_{su} &= \begin{vmatrix} -X_s & U_s & -X_m & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & X_m \\ -X_m s & 0 & -X_r s & R_r \\ 0 & 0 & R_r & X_r s \end{vmatrix} = U_s s X_m^2 R_r; \\ \Delta_{rv} &= \begin{vmatrix} -X_s & 0 & U_s & 0 \\ 0 & X_s & 0 & X_m \\ -X_m s & 0 & 0 & R_r \\ 0 & X_m s & 0 & X_r s \end{vmatrix} = U_s X_m (X_s X_r - X_m^2) s^2; \\ \Delta_{ru} &= \begin{vmatrix} -X_s & 0 & -X_m & U_s \\ 0 & X_s & 0 & 0 \\ -X_m s & 0 & -X_r s & 0 \\ 0 & X_m s & R_r & 0 \end{vmatrix} = -U_s s X_m X_s R_r. \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Substitute (21) into (19) and get the expression:

$$P_s = \frac{3}{2} X_m \left(\frac{\Delta_{sv} \Delta_{ru} - \Delta_{su} \Delta_{rv}}{\Delta^2} \right). \quad (23)$$

If in (23) instead of the determinants we substitute their expressions (22), then after transformations we arrive at a formula that allows us to express the active power in terms of electric voltage and slip

$$P_s = \frac{3}{2} \frac{X_m^2 R_r U_s^2 s}{(X_s X_r - X_m^2)^2 s^2 + X_s^2 R_r^2}. \quad (24)$$

Reactive power (16) taking into account (18) will turn into the form

$$Q_s = \frac{3U_s^2}{2X_s} + \frac{P_s s}{R_r} (X_r - k_s X_m). \quad (25)$$

We substitute value (24) into formula (25) and obtain

$$Q_s = \frac{3U_s^2}{2X_s} + \frac{3}{2} \frac{X_m^2 U_s^2 s^2}{X_s} \frac{(X_s X_r - X_m^2)}{(X_s X_r - X_m^2)^2 s^2 + X_s^2 R_r^2}. \quad (26)$$

We solve equation (24) for sliding s as a quadratic and obtain formula for its determination

$$s = m_1 U_s^2 - \sqrt{m_1^2 U_s^4 - m_2}, \quad (27)$$

where $m_1 = \frac{3R_r X_m^2}{4P_s (X_s X_r - X_m^2)^2}$; $m_2 = \frac{X_s^2 R_r^2}{(X_s X_r - X_m^2)^2}$.

By substituting slip (27) into formula (26) and performing some transformations we finally obtain an expression for the reactive power AM as a function of the stator voltage

$$Q_s = m_3 U_s^2 + \frac{m_3 k_s k_r U_s^2 (m_1 U_s^2 - \sqrt{m_1^2 U_s^4 - m_2})^2}{(1 - k_s k_r) [(m_1 U_s^2 - \sqrt{m_1^2 U_s^4 - m_2})^2 + m_2]}, \tag{28}$$

where $m_3 = \frac{3}{2X_s}$.

The reactive power AM is determined by the sum of two terms: the magnetizing reactive power (the first term in (28)) and the scattering reactive power (the second term in (28)). At high voltages the reactive power of magnetization has a decisive influence and at low voltages the reactive power of dissipation prevails. It follows from the above that expression (28) as a function of the stator voltage has a minimum point, the coordinates of which will change at different values of the active power.

In the paper the functions $Q_s(U_s)$ are calculated without taking into account the effect of saturation of the magnet wire and taking into account this effect. In [4] the following dependence of the inductance of the magnetization circuit on the magnitude of flux coupling was used:

$$L_m = 1,504 L_{mn} \left(\frac{\Psi_s}{\Psi_{sn}} \right) \text{ctg} \left(\frac{\Psi_s}{\Psi_{sn}} \right) = a \Psi_s \text{ctg}(b \Psi_s), \tag{29}$$

where $a = 1,504 L_{mn} / \Psi_{sn}$; $b = 1 / \Psi_{sn}$.

Using expression (9) let's transform formula (29) into the form

$$X_m = a U_s \text{ctg}(b U_s), \tag{30}$$

where $a = 1,504 X_{mn} / U_{sn}$; $b = 1 / U_{sn}$.

Figure 1 – Graphs of the dependence (28) of the reactive power of an asynchronous machine on the magnitude of the stator supply voltage at different active powers: solid line – taking into account the saturation of the magnet wire; dashed line – without taking into account the saturation of the magnet wire

Calculations were made for an asynchronous machine with the following passport data: $P_n = 250kVt$; $U_{ln} = 380V$; $n = 3000rpm$; $s_n = 0,02$; $\eta = 0,925$; $\cos\varphi_{sn} = 0,9$. For other asynchronous machines the results are similar. Figure 1 shows graphs of the dependence of AM reactive power on the stator supply voltage. All values are presented in relative units: $q_s = Q_s/S_n$, $u_s = U_s/U_{sn}$, $p_s = P_s/P_n$. Taking into account the saturation of the magnet wire consists in the fact that the inductive resistance of the

magnetization circuit X_m is not assumed to be constant but is calculated as a function of the stator voltage according to expression (30). From the graphs in Figure 1 it can be seen that at voltages below the nominal the effect of saturation of the magnetic circuit is not detected and the graphs practically coincide. At voltages above the nominal the magnetizing current begins to increase rapidly and with it the reactive power. The curves have a clearly expressed extreme character and when the active power decreases the minimum points shift along the plane (u_s, q_s) in the direction of decreasing reactive power and voltage.

Figure 2 – Dependence of the stator voltage values at which the function (28) $Q_s(U_s)$ reaches a minimum on the active power AM

The article calculates the geometric location of the minimum points of the function (28) at different active powers. To construct such a dependence, shown in Figure 2, a number of values of active power P_s were set. At the same time only the coefficient m_1 in expression (28) changes. Next the golden ratio method was used to search for the voltage U_s at which the function (28) reaches a minimum. In this way the dependence $u_s^*(p_s)$ of the extreme values of the stator voltage on the active power is obtained. The graph of this dependence is close to linear.

Conclusions. In the paper based on the system of AM equations the dependence of the AM reactive power on the supply voltage of the network is derived. Mathematical properties of the function $Q_s(U_s)$ with physical substantiation of its unimodality and the presence of a minimum point were studied. The obtained expression $Q_s(U_s)$ makes it possible to determine the

magnitude of the controlling influence on the high-speed reactive power compensation devices for stabilizing the voltage level in the power supply unit.

References

1. Сегеда М.С. Електричні мережі та системи. Львів: Львівська політехніка, 2009. 492с.
2. Иванов В.С., Соколов В.И. Режимы потребления и качество электроэнергии систем электрообеспечения промышленных предприятий. Москва: Энергоатомиздат, 1987. 336с.
3. Ключев О. В., Садовой О. В., Сохіна Ю. В. Системы керування асинхронними вентилями каскадами. – Кам'янське: ДДТУ, 2018. 294с.
4. Ключев О.В., Садовой О.В. Оптимизация энергетических характеристик асинхронного вентиляльного каскада. *Збірник наукових праць Дніпродзержинського державного технічного університету (технічні науки)*. Дніпродзержинськ: ДДТУ, 2016. Вип. 1(28). С.73-81.